

Heritability (broad sense) and genetic gain in rice.

Character	Cross ^a	Heritability (%)	Genetic gain (%)
Days-to-heading	1	93.5	12.2
	2	81.2	13.0
	3	92.0	12.0
Plant height	1	66.0	12.0
	2	38.0	5.0
	3	32.3	7.4
Effective tillers/plant	1	84.2	64.3
	2	87.5	80.4
	3	89.5	76.8
Panicle length	1	32.0	5.0
	2	43.0	6.0
	3	33.2	3.6
No. of filled grains per panicle	1	91.2	54.8
	2	90.5	58.7
	3	97.0	61.7
Straw weight	1	97.0	87.8
	2	90.4	100.0
	3	93.4	91.0
100-grain weight	1	89.0	28.0
	2	65.0	11.0
	3	76.4	13.5
Grain length	1	25.5	29.1
	2	79.6	10.0
	3	38.6	40.5
Yield/plant	1	90.3	86.9
	2	91.5	94.6
	3	98.5	87.4

^a 1 = Kanchi/Jayanti, 2 = Ratna/Jayanti, 3 = IET1136/Ratna.

gains and high heritability, indicating non-additive gene action. Similar gene action was observed in plant height of Kanchi/Jayanti and grain length of Ratna/Jayanti. □

NDR80, a semitall, nonlodging rice

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At NDUAT we developed NDR80, a semitall, nonlodging, stiff-strawed rice with 115-d maturity. It averages 100 cm tall and is resistant to most foliage diseases. This line has high yield potential and adaptability for irrigated cultivation in India (see table). It has long bold grains with white kernels and has yielded consistently more than check varieties and other new rices. Semitall height helps

Performance of NDR80 (IET7626) in 1982 and 1983 wet season in All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program trials in India.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)			CD 0.05
	NDR80	Ratna	Rasi	
	<i>1982</i>			
Aduthurai	5.4	2.5	2.6	0.8
Coimbatore	3.5	3.3	3.2	0.7
Hyderabad	5.8	5.4	5.1	1.1
Cuttack	2.5	1.2	1.6	0.8
Jeypore	5.4	4.3	4.9	1.4
Karimganj	4.2	3.2	3.6	0.7
Agartala	3.7	2.7	3.1	0.2
Faizabad	5.2	3.1	5.6	1.4
Varanasi	4.6	3.4	3.5	1.1
Patna	4.1	3.0	3.8	0.5
Pantnagar	6.2	3.3	3.5	1.1
Kapurthala	6.0	2.4	3.5	0.9
Gurdaspur	5.8	4.0	4.7	0.9
Kaul	5.6	3.5	4.0	0.7
Nawagaon	6.5	5.1	6.1	0.8
Mean	5.0	3.4	3.9	
Mean d to 50% flowering	91	91	37	
	<i>1983</i>			
	NDR80	Rasi	IR36	
Mannuthy	4.8	3.3	3.9	1.3
Pattambi	3.1	1.8	3.0	0.9
Aduthurai	5.8	4.4	5.2	0.4
Coimbatore	4.6	5.5	5.3	0.9
Pondichery	4.5	2.3	3.8	1.3
Cuttack	4.6	1.8	3.6	0.8
Chinsurah	3.7	1.8	3.1	1.0
Karimganj	3.3	2.2	3.1	0.4
Raipur	3.0	1.8	2.9	0.8
Rewa	4.1	2.5	4.0	0.3
Kanke	2.4	2.1	2.5	0.6
Faizabad	4.7	3.1	3.6	0.9
Varanasi	2.5	2.0	2.8	0.9
Pantnagar	4.1	3.4	2.8	1.1
Kaul	4.8	3.0	3.3	1.2
Banswara	5.9	3.9	5.3	1.2
Kota	4.9	3.0	4.7	1.0
Karjat	2.1	1.8	2.2	0.4
Nawagaon	4.6	3.9	4.6	1.2
Mean	4.1	2.8	3.7	

it compete with weeds at early growth stages. At demonstration plots in Uttar

Pradesh, farmers have chosen NDR80 because of high grain and straw yield. □

Yield evaluation of major indigenous rice varieties grown on Cuu Long Delta

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Much of the Cuu Long Delta still is planted to indigenous rice varieties that yield 1.5-4.5 t/ha. In 1982 and 1983 we surveyed yields of major indigenous rices grown in Cuu Long and Hau Giang Pro-

vinces. Crop-cut samples were from 10 m² plots and mean yields were recorded.

In 1982 in Cuu Long, we took 407 samples of 52 varieties (Table 1). Where rice grows in fresh water, Trang Chum yielded well in fields flooded 31-70 cm deep.

Nang Cho and Nang Trich performed better in 71-cm-deep water. In fields influenced by salinity intrusion (5-8 mo freshwater regime), Lua Phi and Trang Lun yielded best.

Table 1. Yields of selected indigenous rice varieties in Cuu Long Province, 1982.

Water depth (cm)	Variety	Crop-cut sample (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Freshwater area</i>			
31-50	Lem Lun	13	3.6
	Trang Chum	11	3.3
51-70	Cho Bien	20	3.5
	Trang Chum	13	3.5
	Chet som	15	3.4
	Tay Lieu	13	3.4
<i>5-8 mo freshwater area</i>			
31-50	Lua Phi	23	2.8
51-70	Trang Lun	10	3.4
	Lua Phi	39	2.7

Table 2. Yields of selected indigenous rice varieties in Hau Giang Province, 1983.

Harvest month	Water depth (cm)	Variety	No. of crop-cut samples	Yield (t/ha)
Jan	31-50	Tang Chum	12	4.5
		Trang Phuoc	12	4.2
		Cho Bien	11	3.8
	51-70	Trang Chum	23	4.6
		Trang Phuoc	23	4.2
		Nang Chet	10	3.2
		Trang Lun	17	3.1
	71-90	Trang Phuoc	14	4.4
		Trang Chum	16	3.2
	Feb	51-70	Ba Tuc	10
Huyet Rong			22	3.2
Duoi Trau			19	3.2
71-90		Duoi Trau	23	2.8
		Mong Chim	12	2.7

In 1983 in Hau Giang, we took 508 samples of varieties (Table 2). Of the varieties harvested in Jan, Trang Chum and Trang Phuoc yielded well at 31-90 cm water depths. Of the late varieties, harvested in Feb, four yielded best. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Root and shoot characters of medium- and long-duration rice genotypes

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We studied variations in the root and shoot characters at different nursery stages in 24 medium-duration (< 140 d) and 35 long-duration (> 140 d) rice genotypes. The nursery was sown in uniform sand at 15-cm interrow spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications in 1982 kharif. The nursery received 0.5-0.22-0.42 kg NPK/100 m² area and was watered daily.

Mean root and shoot performance of medium-duration rices, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Genotype	Root length (cm)			Root dry wt (mg)			Root volume (cm ³)		Shoot dry wt (mg)		
	10 d	20 d	30 d	10 d	20 d	30 d	20 d	30 d	10 d	20 d	30 d
	IR52	4	14	13	15	125	210	0.8	0.8	10	179
IET3116	7	9	12	19	25	50	0.3	0.3	12	51	112
IET7231	8	13	12	12	52	129	0.5	0.6	21	74	255
IR1561-228-3-3	4	7	6	10	31	19	0.2	0.1	15	36	47

Root and shoot performance of long-duration rices. A. P., India.